

Temperature Based Cooling Fan

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide an outline of a self-contained automated fan speed controller that can regulate the electric fan's speed in accordance with our specifications. Improved efficiency and dependability are achieved via the use of embedded technologies in this closed loop feedback control system. Using an Arduino UNO and an LM35 temperature sensor, this project controls and monitors the speed of a fan based on the surrounding temperature. Here, an LCD screen makes the system easy to operate, while a microprocessor regulates the electric fan's speed as needed for quicker control. The sensed temperature in Celsius and the fan speed in % are both shown on the LCD screen at the same time.

Keywords: Things like fans, LM35 temperature sensors, Arduino, and UNO

1. Introduction

Using temperature differences as a control signal for the fan speed is the basic premise of the project. Altering the fan's temperature provides an alternative method of controlling the motor's speed. It entails taking readings of the item's temperature and making adjustments to the flow of heat energy into or out of the object such that its temperature remains constant. The design and modelling of a room temperature-based PWM fan speed control system are the focus of this research. Any way to find out what the temperature is in a room? A temperature sensor may help you answer that basic question. It has been

used to gauge the ambient temperature, and the Pulse Width Modulation method is employed to adjust the fan's speed in response to the measured temperature.

Proposed System:

2. When it comes to developing smart systems, the microcontroller is king in this project. In today's technological world, it is indispensable. The topic of temperature-based fan speed control in an Arduino system is covered in this article. Based on the current temperature in the room, this device will automatically turn on and off the air conditioner. In order to add a control system to this project, an Arduino board is necessary. It is suggested that this be implemented in order to regulate the fan speed via temperature adjustments made possible by the Internet of Things.

2.

Explanation:

If you have an Arduino board and other electrical components on hand, you can complete this project—temperature-based fan speed control. Since the Arduino UNO board is ubiquitous in electrical circuits, we used it to operate the fan speed control. According to the specifications, the intended system may take readings from the room's temperature and transmit them to an Arduino UNO board. Afterwards, the Arduino UNO board compares the current temperature to the specified temperature using the built-in programme that we provide. An LCD display is linked to an Arduino UNO board using the o/p port, which is used to transmit the operation's

particularly for long periods of time. Ensures that energy is not wasted when a fan is not necessary due to low temperatures. In order to facilitate the automated adjustment of the fan speed for those with disabilities. More characteristics, such as light and humidity, will be able to be monitored and controlled simultaneously in the future, and this data will be able to be sent to a distant place by mobile or the internet. We can use this technology to create computer graphs showing how these factors vary. The automated dialer system will contact the specified number when the temperature rises above a certain threshold.

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